

Experimental Determination and Characterization of Wax Fractions Precipitated as a Function of Temperature

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Published on: Energy & Fuels 22:2 (2008) 708–714

<https://doi.org/10.1021/ef7003927>

Abstract

Wax precipitation at low temperatures in petroleum mixtures is one of the most important problems in flow assurance. Experimental quantification of such process and the further characterization of the precipitated mixtures are very difficult and extremely time consuming and therefore the available experimental information is scarce and usually not very confident. In this work, wax samples were precipitated from two crude oils at different temperatures and they were characterized by optical microscopy, elemental analysis, ^1H NMR spectroscopy, differential scanning calorimetry, and mass spectroscopy. Obtained results show the presence of different compounds in such mixtures regarding the chemical nature of the crude oil. The well known presence of soaked crude oils in the precipitated fractions was experimentally estimated from ^1H NMR and mass spectroscopy and the obtained results suggest the decrease in the soaked crude oil amount as the precipitation temperature becomes lower, in agreement with the qualitative paraffinic content determined by elemental analysis.

These values were used to correct the amount of solid wax precipitated experimentally and the final comparison between such corrected values and the precipitation curve calculated from DSC results shows a good agreement within the high experimental uncertainties.

Keywords: Wax characterization, wax precipitation, wax porosity.

1. Introduction

The precipitation of waxes from petroleum mixtures at low temperatures may cause different problems during production, transport in pipelines or storage. Such problem is well-known within the petroleum industry and a big research effort is made¹⁻⁴ in order to develop procedures to anticipate potential wax deposition problems and to reduce its effects through possible solutions.

The modeling of the precipitation process requires a good knowledge of the liquid-solid equilibrium involved. Although different authors have successfully developed thermodynamic models to describe wax precipitation^{1,5-8}, the research on this field is ongoing and new developments have been reached⁹⁻¹². The main problem is the scarcity of experimental information available which limits the application of such models. Therefore, new reliable experimental data are needed to check the predictive capabilities of such models.

The detailed study of wax deposition involves the experimental determination of two variables: the Wax Appearance Temperature (WAT) and the amount of wax precipitated as a function of temperature (wax precipitation curve, WPC). Different methods have been reported in the literature to precipitate waxes using different solvents and experimental conditions¹³⁻¹⁶. Recently, a new method to carry out the wax precipitation has been developed¹⁷. Such method is based on a multistage fractional precipitation process without dilution of the crude oil and it allows to obtain the precipitation curve for crude oils with different wax content.

Nevertheless, the knowledge of wax composition is also crucial to develop a reliable thermodynamic model to address wax precipitation and deposition¹⁶. Petroleum waxes are mainly formed by n- and iso-alkanes (C₂₀-C₆₀) and represent the major risks to produce wax deposition problems in crude oil flow because of its low solubility in this

medium. According to their composition, crystal structure and physical properties, waxes are usually classified into paraffinic waxes, microcrystalline waxes and petrolatums¹⁹. However, it is common only to distinguish between macro and microcrystalline waxes. Macrocrystalline waxes are mainly n-alkanes with length chain within C₂₀-C₆₀. Microcrystalline or amorphous waxes present a high proportion of iso-paraffins and naphthenes within the range C₃₀-C₆₀⁵. Consequently, further characterization of the precipitated mixtures is needed to have a good knowledge of the properties of precipitated compounds. Different experimental techniques such as differential scanning calorimetry (DSC), Fourier-transformed infrared spectroscopy (FTIR), gas chromatography, (GC) and elemental analysis have been used in order to characterize precipitated waxes^{14,16,19,20,21}. Such characterization was applied to waxes precipitated from bitumen obtaining interesting information²². However, such characterization has been mainly focused on n-paraffins obtained after refining the raw precipitated products, while the analyses of raw precipitated solid have not been reported. The results of characterizing the raw precipitates are of great interest as they can provide information on the kind and distribution of other compounds that may co-precipitate (iso-paraffins and naphthenes) and are present in the precipitated solid.

On the other hand, it is well known that a high amount of entrapped crude oil remains within the precipitated waxes, which in fact has a big effect on the total amount of solid-like phase formed. The quantification of such occluded oil is described through the wax porosity, but the experimental determination it is not well established and it is not usually reported. However, wax porosity should be of major interest to be included in the predictive models.

This study aims to show the application of new methods to obtain precipitated fractions and the further characterization of the raw waxy solids. This can be of great

interest to check new models and to anticipate solutions for future problems caused by wax deposition.

In this work, the characterization of the fractions obtained by precipitating two different crude oils using a multistage fractional precipitation procedure¹⁷ was carried out. Microscopy micrographs have shown how the decrease of the precipitation temperature makes individual crystals become a solid gel. The mixtures have been analyzed by DSC to show the variation of the WAT for each precipitated fraction. Elemental analysis has provided the C/H ratio for each fraction. ¹H-NMR analysis has been used to estimate the aromatic content and the CH₂/CH₃ ratio of each sample, which gives information about the entrapped oil and the branching degree in each precipitated fraction. Gas chromatography-mass spectrometry analysis has shown the decrease in the average n-paraffin size precipitated when decreasing temperature and the presence of entrapped crude oil in the precipitated mixtures.

Results obtained by different techniques show that the content of paraffins increases when decreasing the precipitation temperature. Likewise, the analysis carried out shows evidence of entrapped crude oil in the precipitated solid. The amount of trapped crude oil was calculated by ¹H NMR and high resolution mass spectroscopy, obtaining similar results. The comparison between experimental and DSC precipitation curves shows clear differences, which are remarkably reduced when the content of entrapped crude oil is corrected in the precipitated mixtures.

2. Experimental Section

Materials. Two crude oils with different chemical nature (crude oil 1, naphthenic; and crude oil 2, paraffinic) and their precipitated fractions at different temperatures previously reported¹⁷ were used for a further characterization. Both crude oils were provided by Repsol-YPF.

Fractional Precipitation. The precipitation of solids at different temperatures was carried out by following a multistage fractional precipitation procedure¹⁷, which is shown in Figure 1. 50 g of crude oil (stream 1) are cooled in a cryostat at a slightly higher temperature than its wax appearance temperature (WAT) for 24 hours. The crude oil is then filtered using a glass microfibre Whatman filter N° 934 during at least 2 hours. The solid phase is washed down with acetone to reduce the soaked crude oil and then is recovered by solution in dichloromethane. This procedure can be repeated 4 or 5 times by decreasing the system temperature around 3-5K in each step.

The main difference between this method and other previously reported in the literature is that crude oil is not diluted with any solvent. This conveniently eliminates the influence of said solvent in the nature and amount of paraffins separated, and allows a better representation in the laboratory of the waxes that precipitate in field operations, where the only reason for wax separation is a temperature decrease. This procedure allows to obtain the solid precipitated at each temperature (wax precipitation curve, WPC) and to determine the wax appearance temperature (WAT), or the wax disappearance temperature (WDT).

Total wax precipitation. Wax precipitation was carried out following a modification¹⁷ of the method reported by Burger¹³.

Optical Microscopy. Samples were analyzed with a Leica Leitz DMRXP optical microscope using a sample magnification of 100.

Elemental Analysis. An Elemetar Vario EL III CHNS analyzer was used to determine the content of C and H of each sample. Analysis is carried out by combustion of the sample with an oxygen flow of 65 ml/min. Combustion gases flow through different columns, they are selectively separated and detected by thermal conductivity. Sulphanilic acid was used as standard for the calibration and analyzed after each

experiment to check the quality of measurements. The precision for each determination was ± 0.3 wt%.

^1H NMR. A Bruker DRX 500 NMR spectrometer (C/H dual 5 mm probe, frequency 500 MHz) was used to quantify different types of hydrogen atoms. Samples were solved in deuterio-chloroform in 5 mm samples tubes. The number of scans was 64, with a 30° pulse and a 1 s delay time between scans.

In this work, percent of H_{ar} (hydrogen atoms in aromatic rings), H_α (hydrogen atoms next to functional groups), H_β (methylene hydrogen atoms) and H_γ (methyl hydrogen atoms) were obtained by integration of the corresponding peak areas. The following chemical shift ranges were considered: H_{ar} (9.2-6.5 ppm), H_α (3.8-1.8 ppm), H_β (1.8-1.03 ppm) and H_γ (1.03-0.4 ppm). Such information can be used to determine aromatic content and degree of branching of the mixtures.

Differential Scanning Calorimetry. The differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) technique is widely described in literature^{5,6,23,24} as a procedure to carry out the experimental quantification of wax precipitation in crude oils. This technique has the advantage of its simplicity and fast response which make it appropriate to develop routine essays. In a typical DSC analysis, a sample is heated/cooled at constant rate, the heat transfer is registered and phase transition can be determined by quantifying the differences in heat flows. The application to crude oil samples presents some experimental difficulties because the signal has a very low-intensity, peaks are broad, high sensitivity is required, the determination of the base line is quite complex, the integration of the thermogram is not clearly defined, etc.

In this work, samples were analyzed with a DSC Mettler-Toledo DSC822e. The temperature profile has three steps. In the first step, the sample is heated from 298 to

353 K at 3 K/min. Second step is a cooling process from 353 to 153 K at 3 K/min. In the last step, the sample is heated from 153 to 353 K at 3 K/min.

A procedure has been developed for calibration and thermogram integration using properties of n-paraffins as reference. The integration process yields the wax appearance temperature (WAT), the wax disappearance temperature (WDT) and the wax precipitation curve (WPC).

Mass Spectroscopy. Mass spectrometry provides detailed information about composition of different kinds of mixtures. In this work, two different techniques were used to qualitatively determine the distribution of n-paraffin for each fraction.

Gas Chromatography-Mass Spectroscopy (GCMS). The equipment was a Varian model 3800 series gas chromatograph (GC) equipped with a factorFour VF-1ms capillary column 30 meters long and 0.25 mm internal diameter which stationary phase consists of a 1%-Diphenil-95%-Dimethylpolysiloxane Copolymer with a film thickness of 0.25 micrometer. The detection was carried out by a Varian 1200 series mass detector using electronic impact at 70 eV. The injection port was set at a temperature of 583 K and the GC oven temperature started at 313 K, is increased at 5 K/min up to 598 K, and finally held for 33 min. The Helium carrier gas flow 1 ml/min.

High Resolution Mass Spectroscopy (HRMS). Samples were analyzed in an Autospec Premier mass spectrometer with chemical ionization. Analyses were carried out within the range 100-1000 at 723 K.

3. Results and discussion

Wax precipitation. Results of fractional precipitation and the total amount of waxes were previously reported¹⁷ and they are shown in Figure 2. The total wax content (wt%) at 253 K was 9.56 % for crude oil 1 and 15.15% for crude oil 2. The WAT for each crude oil was calculated obtaining a value of 284 K and 294 K for crude oil 1 and 2,

respectively. Likewise remarkable differences were obtained in the slope of their precipitation curves. Obtained results show differences between both crude oils regarding their different chemical nature.

In this work, precipitated mixtures at each temperature were analyzed by the different experimental techniques reported above.

Optical microscopy. Optical microscopy was used in order to analyze any variation in the crystal size for the different precipitated mixtures. Figure 3 shows the micrographs obtained for the raw crude oil 2 at 298 K and that for the fractions precipitated from this crude oil at 278 K, 273 K and 253 K. As it can be observed, when the precipitation temperature is decreased, the size of wax crystals is larger, individual crystals are not isolated and the resulting structure is more compact.

Elemental analysis. The elemental composition in carbon (C) and hydrogen (H) for each crude oil and all the precipitated mixtures were analyzed and summarized in Table 1. Calculated H/C (mol/mol) ratio is slightly lower than 2 in all the samples, thus showing the presence of both paraffinic and aromatic compounds. H/C (mol/mol) ratio obtained for the precipitated samples shows a slight increase when the precipitation temperature decreases, revealing the diminution of aromatic content in such mixtures. This is in agreement with the value obtained for the mixture precipitated at 253 K (total wax precipitation), which shows the highest H/C, corresponding to the highest paraffin content.

Assuming that solid wax did not contain aromatic compounds and the aromatic content is directly related to the amount of entrapped oil, the above elemental analysis results shows that the content of entrapped oil in the precipitated fractions decreases when the precipitation temperature decreases.

Proton Nuclear Magnetic Resonance Spectroscopy. The content of the different type of hydrogen atoms was obtained by integrating $^1\text{H-NMR}$ spectra. Table 2 shows the results obtained for each sample in weight percent. The CH_2/CH_3 ratio (H_β/H_γ) for each precipitated mixture is also listed.

The same assumption proposed above was followed, solid wax is supposed to contain negligible amount of aromatic hydrogen atoms, so the H_{ar} are only due to the presence of entrapped oil. By comparing the amount of aromatic hydrogen atoms in each precipitated fraction with that in the raw crude oil, it is possible to obtain an estimation of the percent of the entrapped crude oil or wax porosity. The porosity (P) in each mixture was estimated in this work by the following expression, assuming that all aromatic hydrogen atoms are related to the entrapped crude oil in samples:

$$P(\text{wt}\%) = 100 - \left(\frac{H_{\text{ar}C} - H_{\text{ar}M}}{H_{\text{ar}C}} \cdot 100 \right) \quad (1)$$

C and M subscripts refer to Crude oil and Precipitated mixture, respectively. Calculated values are also listed in Table 2.

The main difficulty when dealing with petroleum mixtures is the low signal/noise ratio obtained for some of the peaks (H_{ar} and H_α), which introduces important errors in the quantification. In this work, an estimation of the involved error in the quantification of each kind of hydrogen atom was carried out. A precipitated paraffin sample was analyzed using different concentrations and number of scans. The statistical treatment of the results yielded the following relative errors: $\varepsilon(H_{\text{ar}}) = \pm 36.9\%$; $\varepsilon(H_\alpha) = \pm 58.9\%$; $\varepsilon(H_\beta) = \pm 4.1\%$ and $\varepsilon(H_\gamma) = \pm 4.5\%$.

Values for the entrapped crude oil given in Table 2 are very considerable, with values mostly higher than 50%. As it is shown in Table 2, the wax porosities of the mixtures from crude oil 1 are higher than that for the mixtures from crude oil 2. This can be

related to the different structure of the precipitated compounds. When samples from the same crude oils are compared, the conclusions are in agreement with those from elemental analysis. The content of entrapped oil in the precipitated fractions decreases when the precipitation temperature decreases, and the lowest values were found for the mixture precipitated with solvent at 253 K.

The given values for the wax porosity have to be taken with caution, as they were calculated from H_{ar} which, as shown above, are affected by a large uncertainty. However, the trend seems to be clear, in the sense that the reduction of aromatic compounds in the mixtures precipitated at lower temperatures shows lower wax porosity values.

The relation between H_{β} (CH_2) and H_{γ} (CH_3) provides information about the degree of branching of the compounds in the different samples. Values obtained for crude oil 1 show a high variation with the precipitation temperature, while they are very similar for crude oil 2. This difference can be attributed to the presence of different compounds in the precipitated fractions of both crude oils. However, such results can be considered only qualitatively because they are affected by the presence of entrapped crude oil, which has been shown to represent a high percentage.

Differential Scanning Calorimetry. Crude oils 1 and 2 and all the precipitated mixtures were analyzed by DSC using the experimental procedure described above and the wax disappearance temperature (WDT) was determined. Thermograms for crude oil 1 and their precipitated mixtures are shown in Figure 4. WDT values for all mixtures are listed in Table 3. As it can be observed, WDT is higher for the precipitated samples than that for the corresponding crude oil, this can be explained because precipitated samples are wax concentrated. In addition, WDT for the fractions decreases as temperature does, since the lower the precipitation temperature the lighter paraffins

crystallize. Some non-regular behavior is obtained in several samples; this can be due to the amount of entrapped crude oil which dilutes paraffin (fraction 1 in Table 2) and/or to the different paraffin structures. In fact, fraction 10 in Table 2 shows an H_{β}/H_{γ} ratio clearly larger than that for the rest of the fractions in crude oil 2, which corresponds to a lower branching degree and consequently a higher melting point²². Fractions 5 and 11 behavior could be explained by the same reason.

Mass Spectroscopy. Selected crude oils and all the precipitated fractions were analyzed by gas chromatography-mass spectroscopy (GCMS) and by high resolution mass spectrometry (HRMS) following the experimental procedures described before.

GCMS spectra for crude oil 2 and several precipitated mixtures are shown in Figure 5. The highest peaks in all the spectra are assigned to n-paraffins. Results for the precipitated samples shows the presence of high intensity peaks due to compounds of high molecular weight, corresponding to the precipitated n-paraffins. Besides, some other low intensity peaks are observed, which are related to lighter compounds (the n-paraffins of the entrapped crude oil). When decreasing the precipitation temperature, it is observed how n-paraffins become more concentrated (higher signals) and they appear within the range of lighter compounds.

HRMS allows obtaining the distribution of different families of compounds present in petroleum mixtures. Figure 6 shows the distribution of carbons for crude oil 1 and several of their precipitated mixtures. Reported results are in good agreement with those obtained by GCMS, showing narrower distributions when decreasing the precipitation temperature. Likewise, results reveal the presence of entrapped crude oil, in good agreement with the results obtained by other experimental techniques.

In this work, in order to make quantification of the wax porosity, it was assumed that n-paraffins until C15 were present only in the crude oil and the contribution of n-

paraffins lower than C15 was subtracted to each precipitated mixture. Calculated entrapped crude oil was 55.0% (wt), 68.7% (wt) and 41% (wt) for the mixtures precipitated at 273 K, 278 K and 283 K, respectively. Such values are similar to those obtained by ^1H NMR technique. Figure 7 shows the distributions of paraffins with the entrapped oil correction for the fractions precipitated at 283 K, 278 K and 273 K. As it can be observed, the maximum of the distribution shifts to lower carbon number as the precipitation temperature decreases. Likewise, the distribution of paraffins is narrower when such temperature decreases.

Wax precipitation curve. One of the most interesting magnitudes to be determined in flow assurance is the wax precipitation curve of crude oils. The experimental determination is extremely time consuming and some alternative procedures have been proposed, as for instance by means of the DSC technique.

Figure 8 shows the comparison between the experimental precipitation curves, the corrected values have taken into account the content of entrapped crude oil and the curve obtained by DSC. The amount of entrapped oil was calculated by ^1H MNR, and in the precipitation corrected values the corresponding error bars were included.

The DSC determination is not affected by the entrapped crude oil because only phase transitions are detected. Consequently, DSC results cannot be in agreement with the yields obtained by fractionation and, as shown in Figure 8, experimental values are clearly greater than those obtained by DSC because the presence of entrapped crude oil in such fractions.

However, when the presence of entrapped crude oil in the fractional precipitation curve is corrected by the amount of entrapped crude oil, the accordance against the DSC precipitation curve can be considered satisfactory within the experimental uncertainty.

In this work, two techniques (^1H NMR, HRMS) yield similar results for such determination and values can be considered a good estimation.

4. Conclusions

Two crude oils and the mixtures obtained by their fractional precipitation at different temperatures were characterized using several experimental techniques. Obtained results show differences between mixtures obtained from both crude oils regarding their different chemical nature.

Paraffin content increases with the precipitation temperature decrease. These results were shown by an increase in H/C ratio measured by elemental analysis and a decrease in aromatic contents obtained by ^1H NMR.

The amount of entrapped crude oil seems to be quite large. This porosity has been estimated by two different techniques (^1H -NMR and mass spectroscopy). Similar results were obtained, although uncertainties are considered to be quite high. Further research should be made in order to obtain more reliable values for this important parameter.

WDT determined by DSC for the different precipitated wax are higher than that for crude oils. However WDT for the several precipitated fractions decrease regularly as precipitation temperature decreases, thus showing how lighter compounds are being precipitated. Similar results are obtained by means of the HRMS analysis when entrapped crude oil is corrected. Likewise, the number of carbon distribution becomes narrower when precipitation temperature decreases.

The experimental wax precipitation curve, once corrected with the estimated porosity, fits quite well with the curve obtained from the integration of DSC thermogram, where only precipitated compounds are measured.

Acknowledgements

The authors thank Repsol-YPF for crude oil supply, the use of experimental facilities and financial support through the research project “Aseguramiento de flujo de crudos de petróleo: Estudio de la precipitación de parafinas”.

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Figure captions

Figure 1. Experimental procedure of fractional precipitation.

Figure 2. Results of experimental fractional precipitation. □ Crude oil 1; ○ Crude oil 2.

Figure 3. Optical microscopy micrographs. (a) Crude oil 1; Precipitated fractions at: (b) 278 K (c) 273 K (d) 253 K.

Figure 4. DSC thermograms for crude oil 1 and its precipitated mixtures.

Figure 5. GCMS spectra. (a) Crude oil 2; Precipitated fractions at: (b) 283 K; (c) 278 K; (d) 273 K.

Figure 6. Distribution of carbons obtained by HRMS. (a) Crude oil 1; Precipitated fractions at: (b) 283 K; (c) 278 K; (d) 273 K.

Figure 7. Distribution of paraffins for precipitated mixtures after entrapped crude oil correction at: (a) 283 K; (b) 278 K; (c) 273 K.

Figure 8. Precipitation curves for crude oil 1 and 2.

Line: DSC

Symbols: ○ Experimental; ● Experimental corrected.

Table 1. Elemental analysis results for the crude oils and the precipitated mixtures.

<i>Sample</i>	<i>T^a (K)</i>	<i>C (wt%)</i>	<i>H (wt%)</i>	<i>H/C (mol/mol)</i>
<i>Crude oil 1</i>				
Crude oil 1	-	86.72	11.65	1.61
Fraction 1	283	86.77	11.67	1.61
Fraction 2	278	86.48	11.84	1.64
Fraction 3	273	86.18	12.09	1.68
Fraction 4	268	86.50	12.05	1.67
Total wax 5	253	86.10	12.35	1.72
<i>Crude oil 2</i>				
Crude oil 2	-	86.63	12.36	1.71
Fraction 6	293	86.58	12.14	1.68
Fraction 7	288	86.67	12.25	1.70
Fraction 8	283	86.51	12.12	1.68
Fraction 9	273	86.57	12.40	1.72
Fraction 10	268	-	-	-
Total wax 11	253	86.41	12.80	1.78

a: precipitation temperature of the sample.

Table 2. ¹H NMR results for the crude oils and the precipitated mixtures.

<i>Sample</i>	<i>T^a (K)</i>	<i>Arom H (wt%)</i>	<i>H_α (wt%)</i>	<i>H_β (wt%)</i>	<i>H_γ (wt%)</i>	<i>H_β/H_γ</i>	<i>Entrapped crude Oil (wt%)</i>
<i>Crude oil 1</i>							
Crude oil 1	-	4.13	10.57	54.23	31.08	1.74	-
Fraction 1	283	3.40	9.36	60.87	26.38	2.31	82.32
Fraction 2	278	2.51	8.02	68.2	21.26	3.21	60.77
Fraction 3	273	2.00	7.45	67.21	23.34	2.88	48.43
Fraction 4	268	2.29	7.21	66.2	24.31	2.72	55.45
Total wax 5	253	2.09	5.81	75.06	17.04	4.40	50.61
<i>Crude oil 2</i>							
Crude oil 2	-	4.23	6.65	59.59	29.53	2.02	-
Fraction 6	293	2.01	7.18	69.2	21.62	3.20	47.52
Fraction 7	288	2.17	8.13	67.42	22.28	3.03	51.30
Fraction 8	283	2.59	6.27	67.34	23.8	2.83	61.23
Fraction 9	273	2.24	7.25	67.78	22.74	2.98	52.96
Fraction 10	268	1.85	6.58	73.74	17.83	4.14	43.74
Total wax 11	253	1.50	5.41	73.49	19.6	3.75	35.46

a: precipitation temperature of the sample.

Table 3. WDT obtained by DSC for the crude oils and the precipitated mixtures.

<i>Fraction</i>	<i>T</i> <i>(K)</i>	<i>WDT</i> <i>(K)</i>
<i>Crude oil 1</i>		
Crude oil 1	-	-
Fraction 1	283	31.25
Fraction 2	278	45.15
Fraction 3	273	42.3
Fraction 4	268	32.95
Total wax 5	253	46.5
<i>Crude oil 2</i>		
Crude oil 2	-	-
Fraction 6	293	43.4
Fraction 7	288	37.1
Fraction 8	283	31.3
Fraction 9	273	29.50
Fraction 10	268	45.3
Total wax 11	253	48.05

Figure 1.

Figure 2.

Figure 3.

Figure 4.

Figure 5.

Figure 6.

Figure 7.

Figure 8.

